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**HYPOGLYCEMIA AMONG THE PATIENTS
PRESENTING IN THE EMERGENCY
DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

Hypoglycemia, also known as low blood sugar, is a fall in blood sugar to levels below normal. This may result in a variety of symptoms, including clumsiness, trouble talking, confusion, loss of consciousness, seizures, or death. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the emergency department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, random blood sugar and different symptoms were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 110 patients presenting in the outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 55 males (50%) and 55 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 33.23 ± 4.13 years. Out of these patients, three patients presented with hypoglycemia. Further workup was advised for them.

Keyword: Hypoglycemia

INTRODUCTION:

Hypoglycemia, also known as low blood sugar, is a fall in blood sugar to levels below normal. This may result in a variety of symptoms, including clumsiness, trouble talking, confusion, loss of consciousness, seizures, or death. Feelings of hunger, sweating, shakiness, or weakness may also be present. Symptoms typically come on quickly. The most common cause of hypoglycemia is medications used to treat diabetes such as insulin and sulfonylureas. Risk is greater in diabetics who have eaten less than usual, exercised more than usual, or drunk alcohol. Other causes of hypoglycemia include kidney failure, certain tumors (such as insulinoma), liver disease, hypothyroidism, starvation, inborn error of metabolism, severe infections, reactive hypoglycemia, and a number of drugs, including alcohol. Low blood sugar may occur in otherwise healthy babies who have not eaten for a few hours.

The glucose level that defines hypoglycemia is variable. In people with diabetes, levels below 3.9 mmol/l (70 mg/dl) are diagnostic. In adults without diabetes, symptoms related to low blood sugar, low blood sugar at the time of symptoms, and improvement when blood sugar is restored to normal confirm the diagnosis. Otherwise, a level below 2.8 mmol/l (50 mg/dl) after not eating or following exercise may be used. In newborns, a level below 2.2 mmol/l (40 mg/dl), or less than 3.3 mmol/l (60 mg/dl) if symptoms are present, indicates hypoglycemia. Other tests that may be useful in determining the cause include insulin and C peptide levels in the blood.

Among people with diabetes, prevention is by matching the foods eaten with the amount of exercise and the medications used. When people feel their blood sugar is low, testing with a glucose monitor is recommended. Some people have few initial symptoms of low blood sugar, and frequent routine testing in this group is recommended. Treatment of hypoglycemia is by eating foods high in simple sugars or taking dextrose. If a person is not able to take food by mouth, glucagon by injection or in the nose may help. The treatment of hypoglycemia unrelated to diabetes includes treating the underlying problem

and a healthy diet. The term "hypoglycemia" is sometimes incorrectly used to refer to idiopathic postprandial syndrome, a controversial condition with similar symptoms that occurs following eating, but with normal blood sugar levels (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the emergency department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, random blood sugar and different symptoms were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 110 patients presenting in the emergency department were included in this study i.e., 55 males (50%) and 55 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 33.23 ± 4.13 years. Out of these patients, three patients presented with hypoglycemia. Further workup was advised for them.

DISCUSSION:

Like most animal tissues, brain metabolism depends primarily on glucose for fuel in most circumstances. A limited amount of glucose can be derived from glycogen stored in astrocytes, but it is consumed within minutes. For most practical purposes, the brain is dependent on a continual supply of glucose diffusing from the blood into the interstitial tissue within the central nervous system and into the neurons themselves.

Therefore, if the amount of glucose supplied by the blood falls, the brain is one of the first organs affected. In most people, subtle reduction of mental efficiency can be observed when the glucose falls below 3.6 mmol/l (65 mg/dl). Impairment of action and judgment usually becomes obvious below 2.2 mmol/l (40 mg/dl). Seizures may occur as the glucose falls further. As blood

glucose levels fall below 0.55 mmol/l (10 mg/dl), most neurons become electrically silent and nonfunctional, resulting in coma. These brain effects are collectively referred to as neuroglycopenia.

The importance of an adequate supply of glucose to the brain is apparent from the number of nervous, hormonal, and metabolic responses to a falling glucose level. Most of these are defensive or adaptive, tending to raise the blood sugar by glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis or provide alternative fuels. If the blood sugar level falls too low, the liver converts a storage of glycogen into glucose and releases it into the bloodstream, to prevent the person going into a diabetic coma, for a short time.

Brief or mild hypoglycemia produces no lasting effects on the brain, though it can temporarily alter brain responses to additional hypoglycemia. Prolonged, severe hypoglycemia can produce lasting damage of a wide range. This can include impairment of cognitive function, motor control, or even consciousness. The likelihood of permanent brain damage from any given instance of severe hypoglycemia is difficult to estimate and depends on a multitude of factors such as age, recent blood and brain glucose experience, concurrent problems such as hypoxia, and availability of alternative fuels. Prior hypoglycemia also blunts the counter-regulatory response to future hypoglycemia. While the mechanism leading to blunted counterregulation is unknown several have been proposed.

Those type 1 diabetics found "dead in bed" in the morning after suspected severe hypoglycemia are often found to have had some underlying coronary pathology that led to an induced fatal heart attack. In 2010, a case report was published demonstrating the first known case of an individual found "dead in bed" whilst wearing a continuous glucose monitor, which provided a history of glucose levels before the fatal event; the person had suffered a severe hypoglycemic incident, and while the authors described only a "minimal counter-regulatory response", they stated no "anatomic abnormalities" were observed during autopsy (4-6).

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